

Selfish Behavior Tendencies in Adolescence

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Abstract: *The article analyzes the manifestations, forms and types of egoism in human behavior. As we know, the topic of adolescence occupies a special place in developmental psychology. In the life of a teenager, social relations, attitudes towards oneself, people, and society begin to form. This article analyzes theoretical views on the manifestation of egoism in adolescence, the reasons for its influence, and fully explains its essence.*

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Philosophers, religious figures and scientists have studied the problem of egoism. Although psychology as an independent science does not have a long history, in some areas of personality behavior and its characteristics one can find views, theories and studies related to egoism. Egoism is one of the main motivational and meaningful characteristics of personality and remains one of the least studied and defined characteristics. Due to the ambiguity of ideas about the nature and essence of the origin of egoism in modern psychology, this concept has not been sufficiently studied. Egoism is often considered a negative characteristic of a person, and the famous philosopher and scientist Pascal wrote about this: Egoism is hateful and people should not be indifferent to it. Philosophers disagree in the study of egoism and describe it as one of the causes of many problems and difficulties that arise between people in society. Various definitions can be found in the studies and definitions of egoism by scientists. In particular, V. Leibin gives the following definition of egoism: "Egoism is a property of a person who wants others to pay attention to his world due to his desires and aspirations. [1; 106-120 p] Another philosopher and scientist, Epictetus, expressing his views on egoism, emphasizes that a person should not act against the interests of others, as long as he does everything for himself. Egoism begins when a person does not care about his own interests, but when he separates his interests from the interests of others and opposes them to each other.

The French writer R. Roland said that if a person wants to live with pleasure through egoism, then the goal will disappear. The scientist K. Muzdibaev, who conducted many studies of the characteristics of the manifestation of egoism in social strata and at different age periods, said that egoism is useful only in relation to other people, that is, interpersonal relationships are useful for oneself, but harmful to others appears in cases when Based on his research, K. Muzdibaev studied a number of characteristics characteristic of egoists. According to him, egoists:

Firstly, they ignore duty, norms and moral laws, and arbitrarily establish rules in their own interests; *secondly*, they are characterized by such negative characteristics as aggressive forms of behavior (fighting, revenge), sexual violence, injustice, lies.

thirdly, they treat other people with malice, envy, vindictiveness, rudeness. This makes it impossible to use constructive communication strategies with such people;

Fourthly, egoists use ineffective ways to overcome life's difficulties, but achieve success, are always pleased with themselves and feel happy.

It is evident that an egoistic person not only satisfies his own interests, but also ignores the interests of others and necessarily creates a conflict situation when satisfying his needs at the expense of others. All concepts of egoism can be conditionally divided into two large groups: biological and social. Within the framework of these approaches, it is advisable to develop motivational components of egoism, effective aspects of egoistic behavior, features of education leading to the development of egoism, and, accordingly, methods of its correction. R. Laut that egoism is a destructive state of personality and emphasizes that the egoist pursues the ideal of destruction for his own benefit. The egoist, says R. Laut, comes to the conclusion that he is ready to violate the laws of society for his own benefit, achieve what he wants by force, and even resort to cunning or open violence to avoid punishment [2; 446 p.].

Egoism is usually characterized by inflated self-esteem and authoritarianism. In his work, G. Kavka tries to make a clear distinction between egoism and identifies two types of egoism, according to which the first is maximum egoism, in which a person always serves his long-term personal interests, he performs actions that bring benefits. he thinks that will serve him well. The second is non-maximized egoism, in which the ultimate goal of any human action is considered to be some benefit [4].

J. Robinson argues that egoism is "the concept of loyalty to one's own interests without regard for the interests of other people and is contrasted with the concept of loyalty to other people and the sacrifice of one's own interests" [5; pp. 38-39].

N. La Follette, expressing his opinion about psychological egoism, mentions that this concept can be a concept derived from the theory of hedonism. In his opinion, psychological egoism means a person's desire to receive high-level pleasure and avoid any pain.

N. Sidgwick uses the term "Reasonable Egoism", the meaning of this concept is that a person expresses his claims to satisfy his interests with the help of reasonable egoism, which means that it should always be associated with common sense. The theory of reasonable egoism arose from the philosophical concepts of such great thinkers as Locke, Hobbes, Puffendorf, Grotius in the 17th century. According to S. Hall, the sharp emergence of the manifestation of egoism, its individual form, the feeling of ownership is accompanied by the child's awareness of his own "I" and his is one of the characteristics of nature. Manifestations of the biogenetic flow should not prevent the manifestation of egoism and lies in the child's behavior, which, in their opinion, can negatively affect his development.

Among the manifestations of psychoanalysis, Z. Freud evaluates the phenomenon of egoism as positive behavior and considers egoism to be the essence of human nature and the main principle of human relations. In his interpretation, egoism manifests itself not only in property, the desire to collect, but also in ordinary needs such as food and clothing. In his fundamental work, *The Interpretation of Dreams*, he notes that a child is born with "primary narcissism" because his libido is initially directed at himself. "The child is completely egoistic, he has a highly developed sense of his own needs, he sees his brothers and sisters as his competitors and tries to use them to satisfy his needs. He also noted that the altruistic inclination continues to develop in the child individually [6; 192-193c]. According to the views of Z. Freud, in adolescence, the libido moves from the person himself to other objects, and the person "about at the stage of "active relations" he moves into the category of altruists, and at the next stage this is manifested by a higher level of interest in himself

compared to the previous one. The point of view of Z. Freud is shared by the American politician E. Hoover. He interprets egoism as a biologically innate feeling, long embedded in human nature and thus justifying the immoral behavior of a person.

J. Piaget compares the development of a child with the struggle of two tendencies: the first is the biological egoism of a child's character, the second is social influences intensively carried out by adults. From here we see that, according to the theory of J. Piaget, the main path of development of the child's mental life consists of egoism and egocentrism up to socialization. Thus, J. Piaget considers egoism as self-love, and evaluates it as behavior aimed primarily at loving others.

A completely opposite view of the nature and origin of egoism has been formed in world psychology since the beginning of the 20th century under the influence of the works of E. Durkheim, J. Tarde, K. Blondel. Supporters of this trend underestimate the role of heredity, raise public consciousness to a higher level in the development of personality. Thus, according to J. Piaget and his supporters, egoism is interpreted as an important sign of personality development as a structural element of personality, developing together with its interests, love and even hatred. According to some researchers, even in a pathological state of a person, along with the weakening of egoistic tendencies, a person can lose interest in himself and others, such states as weakness and psychological poverty can intensify [8; 116-129]

Modern science claims that man is not social, but an innate biological factor of man's desire for self-preservation and self-affirmation. From the point of view of evolution, all living beings have an innate desire to adapt to the environment in order to increase their chances of survival. From a biological point of view, writes G. Rakhlin, egoism manifests itself as a struggle for survival . Therefore, any egoistic decision initially seems preferable to the individual than any altruistic decision . Abroad, spiritual psychology is characterized by an ambiguous, dual attitude towards egoism. Other modern studies suggest that the subject needs egoistic motivation and self-care. In this regard, we quote the work of E. Fromm: "Modern culture is full of taboos on egoism. We are taught that being selfish is a sin, but loving others is good."

As S. Holmes noted, the study of egoism abroad has been conducted over the centuries in two different directions. Egoism, on the one hand, arises as a result of competition between people and worsens relations between them, on the other hand, it is perceived as a necessary "engine" of any human action.

As it turned out, egoism entered academic psychology a long time ago, and among foreign researchers of this topic, Z. Freud, neo-Freudians (G. Sullivan, K. Horney, E. Fromm), humanistic psychologists (A. Maslow, K. Rogers), the founders of social learning theories (A. Bandura), as well as other modern areas of social psychology and psychotherapy, emphasized the superiority of the ideology of egoism. According to Z. Freud, individual development of a person is initially egoistic behavior, which is manifested in the actions of each person aimed at personal happiness, and then - altruistic actions carried out in interaction with others.

Half a century before Freud's work, the German philosopher A. Schopenhauer considered egoism to be the source of the "will to live". According to A. Shaftesbury, the harmony of affects determines whether a person plays the role of an egoist or an altruist. In his opinion, a person is born with three types of affect:

- a natural inclination towards the good of society;
- a selfish tendency that seeks only personal gain;
- the so-called neutral tendencies (they are neither egoistic nor altruistic)

The opposite concept of egoism is altruism, which is understood as the ability of a person to sacrifice his own interests for the sake of the interests of another person. This term was introduced by the French philosopher O. Comte as a concept opposite to egoism.

L. Feuerbach said that the highest goal of a person is to take care of himself, without which he cannot manifest himself as a person in society. Consequently, egoism or selfishness also represents the essence of human nature. L. Feuerbach's teaching is aimed at protecting personal interests, i.e. in favor of egoism, and denies asceticism (a psychological defense mechanism). Taking care of oneself does not exclude taking care of another person, and egoism presupposes altruism, which is its starting point, he says .

According to E. Hoffman's concept, egoism is not a personal interest, but a state that helps a person satisfy his own needs. In his opinion, egoism can never be eliminated because it is connected with nature itself, with human nature . Thus, philosophers supported a number of ideas in explaining the nature of egoism, but they failed to solve the problem of egoism scientifically. Egoism is often confused with closely related moral concepts such as profit, pleasure, and interest.

The doctrine based on the cultural-historical and operational theories of studying egoism was put forward by Russian scientists L.S. Vygotsky, A.N. Leontiev, S.L. Rubinstein, and according to it, opinions were put forward that living conditions and upbringing play a decisive role in the development of a child. E.F. Petrov was the first in literature to systematically describe the nature of egoism, its socio-economic, political, philosophical and epistemological roots [9; 207-c]. The scientist considers this concept as a result of the division of private property and society into classes. The role of specific social conditions in the prevalence of egoistic motives in a particular society is shown.

V. N. Myasishchev considered egoism from the point of view of the theory of relations, the nature of education and its determining factors, including lack of love, rudeness, hostility towards the child, lack of friends, neediness, illness of parents, other family problems. due to the presence of preferred children, lack of criticality, compassion, excessive activity or slowness of the individual, manifestation of personal self-protective tendencies. passes, in his opinion, the emergence of an egoistic institution in a subject occurs as a result of a combination of some of the above conditions and partially endogenous personality traits.

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